

THEORETICAL VIEWS ON ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6506658>

Ibraimova Go'zal Baxtiyor qizi

2rd year undergraduate student

Termez State University

gozalibraimova@com

Keywords: *proverbs, sayings, parema, folklore, expressive means, riddle*

One of the factors that characterizes the national values and culture of the people is the oral tradition of the people. Proverbs, one of the most important genres of folklore, are one of the most important topics studied in linguistics and have great importance today.

This article focuses on the universal features of Uzbek and English proverbs and their similarities and differences compared to the other genres of folklore. We will also look at the linguistic aspects of Uzbek and English folk proverbs and get acquainted with the theories of scholars working in this field.

Folk proverbs, which emerged as a peculiar phenomenon of language, philosophy, and artistic creation, are a genre of folklore with a concise form but a deep meaning.

Such layers of art, each of which can demonstrate the beauty of our language, the subtlety of our speech, the intellect and the logic of our thinking with astonishing power, are a unique mirror of the centuries-old life experiences and way of life of our people. In this artistic mirror you can see, attitude towards life, nature, man, family and society, socio-political, spiritual-enlightenment, moral-aesthetic and philosophical views, [61; 3]

For this reason, proverbs have become so widespread that they have been used for centuries not only in live speech and interpersonal communication, but also in artistic, historical and scientific works, political and journalistic literature, and are still widely used today.

Proverbs are a common independent genre of oral art as rare examples of folk wisdom. Conditionally, they are public morality. can be called rules of etiquette.

Proverbs are the result of a very concise, and figurative expression of the socio-political, spiritual, cultural, moral and philosophical views of the people, which have been tested in the life experiences of centuries. Proverbs are not specifically created, but emerge as a judgment as a moral value of a conclusion drawn from life experience tested by the demands of a particular circumstance. They show that in the course of human activities in various fields, the product of long-term life experiences has emerged as a stable and unchanging, correct and true conclusion.

In English, the word proverb is usually expressed by the word "proverb". Sometimes in many literatures: adages, dictums, maxims, mottoes, precepts, saws, truisms, we can also give the concept of a proverb. Like Uzbek folk proverbs, English folk proverbs are one of the most common genres of English folklore. It often has general features similar to Uzbek proverbs in its structure, study in folklore, and so on.

When referring to folk proverbs, one must take into account their historicity. Because many of the proverbs we use in our speech today were created in the past, they are a clear expression of the limitations and contradictions of popular psychology, worldview. Therefore, it is necessary to collect folk proverbs, to study their layers in nature from the point of view of consistent class.

A proverb if it is used in the speech of a working people, it serves the interests of that class, or vice versa. The translation of the proverb is that a fool's bow is shot quickly. If we look at the translation, there is no doubt that the proverb was created in the distant past.

Due to changes in social life, the content of proverbs changes at different levels - narrowing or widening. This fact alone shows that the proverb is directly related to the life of society, the life of the people. [55; 93]

This means that proverbs play a key role in the study of people's lives, their past economic, political and cultural life. Indeed, proverbs objectively assess different socio-economic relations, ethical and aesthetic norms of the people, religious beliefs, way of life and work, love and hate, dreams and aspirations. The famous Russian writer LN Tolstoy once said, "In every proverb I see the image of the people who created this proverb," Another important aspect of proverbs is that they are exemplary. Proverbs always say an exemplary thought. But just as any exemplary thought cannot be a proverb, there are a number of conditions under which exemplary thought can become a proverb.

They are as follows:

An exemplary idea that turns into a proverb is that it has been tested in the life experience of the people for many years. Any thought tested in life experience can be convincing;

The exemplary idea expressed in the proverb has a universal character, not only for the individual;

The tested universal idea must have a concise, perfect artistic form. [55; 93]

It is for these reasons that folk proverbs tend to be created and forgotten very slowly.

These characteristics are realized in relation to the economic, political and cultural structure of a society, the degree of stability or instability of that structure.

The instructive nature of the proverbs makes them more vivid and powerful. For example: "A bad execution is better than none" in Uzbek - to apologize reluctantly is better than not apologizing at all. As an Uzbek alternative, we cite the proverb "Get out

of the snake's nest with a good word, get out of the Muslim religion with a bad word." As you can see, these proverbs have a very instructive meaning. That is, a person should always be sweet-spoken and well-spoken. Both versions of the proverb have the same meaning.

An important factor in the study of proverbs is how they are structured and how they are formed through syntactic units. Proverbs are based on one or more syntactic units.

Proverbs that consist of a single syntactic whole are usually considered to be one-part sentences and are often in the form of sentences. Uzbek and English folk proverbs are very similar in this respect. For instance The absent is always in the wrong- O'zi yo'qning $\square$ ko'zi yo'q.

There is no accounting for tastes -Har kim suygan oshini ichadi.

Actions speak louder than words-Gap bilguncha $\square$ ish bil

Advise none to marry or go to war-Har kimning niyati o'zining yo'ldoshi.

Most proverbs consist of two parts, one descriptive and the other concluding:

After dinner sit a while, After supper walk a mile.

Qorning ochmasdan ovqat yegin, Qorning to'ymasdan qo'l artgin.

Art is long, life is short.

Ilmsiz $\square$ bir yashar, Ilmli $\square$ ming yashar.

English and Uzbek folk proverbs are studied in the field of paremiology of folklore and differ from other genres of folklore with a number of peculiarities. That is, in them the idea is expressed in the form of a clear, complete conclusion, a concise sentence, the expression of a particular sentence in a logical sequence, sharp polarity, and is able to be applied in its own and figurative senses. In addition, the proverbs show their universal nature through the predominance of aspects such as exemplary, instructive.

Through a comparative study of the history of the study of Uzbek and English proverbs in folklore, we have seen in which language their level of study is perfect or shallow. Mahmud Kashgari's collection work in the Uzbek language and his work "Devoni lug'otit turk" are a good example of this. The Bible, also known as the Book of Proverbs in English, is a collection of English folk sayings quoted by ancient ancestors. These two sources are ancient proverbs that have survived to the present day.

REFERENCES:

1. Ilyish B. The Structure of Modern English. $\square$ L.: Prosvesheniye, 1971. $\square$ 366 p.
2. Imomov K., Mirzayev T., Sarimsoqov B., Safarov O. O'zbek xalq og'zaki poetik ijodi. -T.: O'qituvchi, 1990. - 303b.
3. Karamatova K.M., Karamatov H.S. Proverbs $\square$ Maqollar–Пословицы. – Т.: Mehnat, –2000. –398 b.
4. Korunets I.V. Theory and Practice of Translating. - Vinnytsia: Nova Knyga, 2001. –265p.
5. Marvin, D.E. Antiquity of Proverbs. - New York and London: G.P Putnam Sons, 1922. –103 p.
6. Madayev O.,

Sobitova T. Xalq og'zaki poetik ijodi. – T.: Sharq, 2010. – 207b. 7. Meider, W. Dundes, A. The Wisdom of Many: Essays on the Proverb. -NewYork: Garland, 1995. –340 p. 8. Mirzayev T., Musoqulov A., Sarimsoqov B. O`zbek xalq maqollari . – T.: